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AYRIM IRRATSIONAL KO'RINISHDAGI FUNKSIYALARNI TRIGONOMETRIK ALMASHTIRISHLAR YORDAMIDA INTEGRALLASH

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Annotatsiya: *Ayrim murakkab ko'rinishdagi ifodalarni integrallash davomida integral ostidagi irratsional funksiyaning ko'rinishiga alohida e'tibor beramiz.*

Quyidagi: $\int R(x, \sqrt{a^2 - x^2})dx, \int R(x, \sqrt{a^2 + x^2})dx, \int R(x, \sqrt{x^2 - a^2})dx$
ko'rinishdagi integrallar, mos ravishda $x = a \sin t, x = a \tan t, x = a \sec t, a \in R, a \neq 0$, almashtirishlar natijasida ratsionallashtirilib hisoblanadi

Kalit so'zlar: *Integral, irratsional funksiya, trigonometrik almashtirishlar.*

$\int R(x, \sqrt{a^2 - x^2})dx, \int R(x, \sqrt{a^2 + x^2})dx, \int R(x, \sqrt{x^2 - a^2})dx$ ko'rinishdagi ifodalarni integrallashni misollarda batafsil ko'rib chiqamiz.

Misollar:

1-misol. $\int (\sqrt{a^2 - b^2 x^2}) dx = \left[t = \arcsin\left(\frac{x}{\frac{a}{b}}\right); x = \frac{a}{b} \sin t; dx = \frac{a}{b} \cos t dt \right]$

$$\int \sqrt{a^2 - b^2 \left(\frac{a}{b} \sin t\right)^2} \frac{a}{b} \cos t dt = \frac{a}{b} \int \sqrt{a^2 - b^2 \left(\frac{a}{b} \sin t\right)^2} \frac{a}{b} \cos t dt =$$

$$\frac{a}{b} \int \sqrt{a^2 - b^2 \frac{a^2}{b^2} \sin^2 t} \cos t dt =$$

$$\frac{a}{b} \int \sqrt{a^2(1 - \sin^2 t)} \cos t dt = \frac{a}{b} \int \sqrt{a^2 \cos^2 t} \cos t dt = \frac{a}{b} \int a * \cos t * \cos t dt =$$

$$\frac{a^2}{b} \int \frac{1 + \cos 2t}{2} dt = \frac{a^2}{2b} \int (1 + \cos 2t) dt = \frac{a^2}{2b} \left(t + \frac{\sin 2t}{2} \right) = \frac{a^2}{2b} \left(\arcsin \left(\frac{x}{a} \right) + \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{\sin \left(\arcsin \left(\frac{x}{a} \right) \right)}{2} \right) = \frac{a^2 \arcsin \frac{bx}{a} + \frac{bx \sqrt{a^2 - b^2 x^2}}{x}}{2b} + C$$

2-misol. $\int \frac{\sqrt{4+x^2}}{x^2} dx = \left[x = 2tg t; t = \arctg \frac{x}{2}; dx = 2 * \frac{1}{\cos^2 t} dt \right] =$

$$\int \frac{\sqrt{4+4tg^2 t} * 2}{8tg^3 t * \cos^2 t} dt = \int \frac{\sqrt{1+tg^2 t}}{2 \frac{\sin^3 t}{\cos t}}$$

$$dt = \int \frac{\frac{1}{\cos t}}{2 \frac{\sin^3 t}{\cos t}} dt = \int \frac{1}{2 \sin^3 t} dt = \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{\sin^2 t + \cos^2 t}{\sin^3 t} dt = \frac{1}{2} \int \left(\frac{1}{\sin t} + \right.$$

$$\left. \frac{\cos^2 t}{\sin^3 t} \right) dt = \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{1}{\sin t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{\cos^2 t}{\sin^3 t} dt = \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{1}{\sin t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \int \cos t * \frac{\cos t}{\sin^3 t} dt =$$

$$= \left[\begin{array}{l} u = \cos t \quad v = -\frac{1}{2 \sin^2 t} \\ du = -\sin t dt \quad dv = \frac{\cos t}{\sin^3 t} dt \end{array} \right] = \frac{1}{2} \int \frac{1}{\sin t} dt + \frac{1}{2} \cos t * \left(-\frac{1}{2 \sin^2 t} \right) -$$

$$\frac{1}{2} \int -\frac{1}{2 \sin^2 t} (-\sin t) dt =$$

$$\frac{\cos t}{4 \sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{4} \int \frac{1}{\sin t} dt = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{4} \int \frac{\sin t}{\sin^2 t} dt = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{4} \int \frac{\sin t}{1 - \cos^2 t} dt = [u = \cos t]$$

$$= -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{4} \int \frac{1}{u^2 - 1} du = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{4} \int \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{u-1} - \frac{1}{1+u} \right) du = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{8} (\ln|u-1| - \ln|1+u|)$$

$$u) = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t} + \frac{1}{8} \ln \left| \frac{\cos t - 1}{\cos t + 1} \right| = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\cos(\arctg \frac{x}{2})}{\sin^2(\arctg \frac{x}{2})} - \frac{1}{8} \ln \left| tg^2 \left(\frac{\arctg \frac{x}{2}}{2} \right) \right| =$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \cos(\arctg \frac{x}{2}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{x^2}{4}}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{4 + x^2}} \\ \sin^2(\arctg \frac{x}{2}) = \frac{x^2}{4 + x^2} \end{array} \right]$$

$$= -\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{\sqrt{4+x^2}}{x^2} + \frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \frac{8+x^2+4\sqrt{4+x^2}}{x^2} \right| \right) = -\frac{1}{4} \left(\frac{2\sqrt{4+x^2}}{x^2} + \frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \frac{8+x^2+4\sqrt{4+x^2}}{x^2} \right| \right) + C$$

3-misol. $\int \frac{\sqrt{a^2+b^2x^2}}{x^2} dx =$

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} x = \frac{a}{b} \operatorname{tg} t \\ dx = \frac{a}{b} \frac{1}{\cos^2 t} dt \end{array} \quad t = \operatorname{arctg} \frac{x}{\frac{a}{b}} \right]$$

$$= \int \frac{\sqrt{a^2+b^2 \frac{a^2}{b^2} \operatorname{tg}^2 t}}{\frac{a^2}{b^2} \operatorname{tg}^2 t} * \frac{a}{b} \frac{1}{\cos^2 t} dt = \int \frac{a\sqrt{1+\operatorname{tg}^2 t}}{\frac{a^2}{b^2} \frac{\sin^2 t}{\cos^2 t}} * \frac{a}{b} \frac{1}{\cos^2 t} dt =$$

$$b \int \frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos^2 t}} * \frac{1}{\sin^2 t} dt = b \int \frac{1}{\sin^2 t (\cos t)} dt =$$

$$b \int \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t \cos^2 t} dt = b \int \frac{\cos t}{\sin^2 t \cos^2 t} dt = b \int \frac{\cos t}{(1-\sin^2 t) \sin^2 t} dt =$$

$$[u = \sin t]$$

$$= b \int \frac{1}{(1-u^2)u^2} du =$$

$$\left[\begin{array}{l} \frac{1}{(1-u^2)u^2} = \frac{A}{(1-u)} + \frac{B}{(1+u)} + \frac{C}{u^2} + \frac{D}{u} \\ 1 = u^2(1+u)A + (1-u)u^2B + (1-u^2)C + (1-u^2)uD \\ A = \frac{1}{2}; D = 0, B = \frac{1}{2}; C = 1 \end{array} \right]$$

$$= b \int \left(\frac{1}{2(1-u)} + \frac{1}{2(1+u)} + \frac{1}{u^2} \right) du = b \left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln|1-u| + \frac{1}{2} \ln|1+u| - \frac{1}{u} \right) =$$

$$b \left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \frac{1-u}{1+u} \right| - \frac{1}{u} \right) = b \left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \frac{1-\sin t}{1+\sin t} \right| - \frac{1}{\sin t} \right) = b \left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \frac{1-\sin(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{xb}{a})}{1+\sin(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{xb}{a})} \right| - \frac{1}{\sin(\operatorname{arctg} \frac{xb}{a})} \right) =$$

$$\left[\sin \left(\operatorname{arctg} \left(\frac{xb}{a} \right) \right) = \frac{bx}{\sqrt{a^2+b^2x^2}} \right]$$

$$= b \left(-\frac{1}{2} \ln \left| \frac{1-\frac{bx}{\sqrt{a^2+b^2x^2}}}{1+\frac{bx}{\sqrt{a^2+b^2x^2}}} \right| - \frac{\sqrt{a^2+b^2x^2}}{bx} \right) + C \quad C \in R;$$

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